

VISUAL REPRESENTATION IN MEDIA DISCOURSE

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Summary: Change and development of phraseological meaning is not merely a feature of illustrations in a literary discourse, as we have seen from Thurber and from Lewis Carroll's Alice's Adventures in Wonderland (a sustained visual pun). Instantial stylistic use is a mode of figuration that is also common to various types of newspaper texts, which easily combine verbal and visual representation in creative thinking.

Key words: to put one's best foot forward, Phraseological metaphors, visualisation techniques, Multimodal metaphor.

Put one's best foot forward:

The PU to put one's best foot forward, which appears in the headline of a news item The Queen puts her best (b a r e) foot forward in The Times (22 April, 1999, p. 1). The headline is instantial use due to insertion of the epithet bare, which appears in brackets. This is highly unusual, as the base form never contains brackets. The brackets become a semantic technique. Moreover, the instantial constituent bare brings out the literal meaning of the constituent foot, which results in a phraseological pun as part of the process of semantic change in the instantiation of the phraseological metaphor. The pun is enhanced by a big photograph of Queen Elizabeth with one of her shoes off (with one bare foot).

To put one's best foot forward is a polysemous PU. One of the meanings is "to make the best possible showing".⁹ When the Queen celebrated her 73rd birthday in Korea she had to observe local custom by removing her white court shoes to enter a traditional house in her stockinged feet. The literal meaning of shoes is spread throughout the news item: the Queen is kicking them off and wriggling her feet back into them again. The phraseological pun permeates the text, contributing to its coherence and cohesion.

Phraseological metaphors:

Phraseological metaphors may be visualised and sustained not only in news items and articles of a general type but also in serious specialist articles, as, for instance, the financial article *Send Your Money Home in Time* (29 September, 1997, p. 44) dealing with interest rates, stocks, and mortgages. The metaphorical focus of the article is the concept home. The idea of home as a desired place to live in is manifest in the use of three phraseological units that share the common constituent home, occurring within the limits of a short article. The first lines read as follows:

Your home has always been your castle, and it used to double as a piggy bank,
Until a classic late-'80s bust crushed the notion of housing as an investment.
Time, 29 September, 1997, p. 44

The article actually deals with the nonfigurative meaning of home, discussing existing homes and house prices and the idea of a house as an investment. The article ends with another PU with the constituent home, creating a frame construction and acting as a coda:

A house as an investment is a pitch that hasn't opened many doors lately.
But today, home isn't just where the heart is; It's where the smart Money
Is too.
Time, 29 September, 1997, p. 44

The base form of the PU home is where the heart is has a positive meaning: your true home is in the place you love most.¹⁰ In the text the PU is used in the opposite meaning. The PU is extended by a parallel construction, which conveys the message of the article: a house is a good investment now. Usually phraseological puns have one or several constituents, which are used in their literal meaning(s). In this case the pun is created through an associative link between a home and a house.

Visualisation techniques:

Use of a symbol is one of the visualisation techniques. For identification of instantial graphic implications, it is important to know the cultural background: The use and symbolic meaning of the currency sign. Graphic properties are generally used to represent the extra-linguistic world in an accurate manner. The visual effect works together with the verbal in creation of a visual pun; it is a way in which "words, typography and pictures are woven together to form multimodal texts" (Goodman and Graddol 1996: 1).

Multimodal metaphor:

Multimodal metaphor is the most common technique of stylistic use of PUs on the Internet. Let me take one PU and examine a number of its visual representations. For instance, over the last decade the Internet has been teeming with various images featuring the PU money laundering. Though this term is informal as to its stylistic level, it is in standard use in criminal law; for example, the official name of the US law is the Money Laundering Statute. Thus, it is a terminological PU or a terminological phraseologism according to Nikulina (2005).

The global culture of using both verbal and nonverbal techniques on the Internet has resulted in multimodal discourse, which resorts to several manifestation modes of expression.¹² This development is also seen in numerous sites dealing with money laundering and conferences dedicated to it (Figures 6.11, 6.12, 6.13). Use of symbols is one visualisation technique that helps to depict the abstract in terms of the concrete multimodal manifestations.

THE LIST OF USED LITERATURE:

1. See Webster's New Universal Unabridged Dictionary ([1983] 1989: 713).
2. See Cambridge International Dictionary of Idioms (1998: 195).
3. See Money laundering is a global problem (2008).
4. For the semiotics of advertising see Beasley and Danesi (2002).